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Data Review

Data Citation

Leonardo Oelgemöller (2025): Review of EBRD (2006–2023): Life in Transition Survey (LiTS I–IV). (published on European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD)), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/69142EDA-5AAE-4A7F-9A6B-55347F783369>

Abstract

The Life in Transition Survey (LiTS), conducted jointly by the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) and the World Bank, is a large-scale, cross-national survey that captures public attitudes and lived experiences in post-socialist and transition countries. Since its first wave in 2006, the survey has been repeated in 2010, 2016, and 2022, covering over 40 countries across Eastern Europe, Central Asia, and beyond. Each wave collects nationally representative data through face-to-face interviews on topics such as political trust, economic satisfaction, institutional confidence, household well-being, and views on democracy and markets.

The survey's design allows for cross-country and over-time comparison, making it an essential resource for the study of social and economic change in post-communist societies. Its relevance is reflected in a growing body of research across fields like political science, sociology, and economics. Scholars have used LiTS data to examine issues ranging from trust in institutions and perceptions of inequality, to democratic support and life satisfaction under transition.

Due to its consistent methodology, multilingual documentation, and open-access data policy, LiTS is a highly reusable dataset. It is particularly valuable for research focusing on transition economies and for comparing social dynamics across regions. This data review summarizes the core structure of the dataset, methodological aspects, coverage, and selected academic applications to illustrate its scholarly importance.

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Data Review: Life in Transition Survey I–IV

The Life in Transition Survey (LiTS) is a survey organized by the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) and supported by the World Bank. It focuses on how people in post socialist countries and nearby regions experience changes in their lives, especially in politics, the economy, and society. The main goal of the survey is to better understand public attitudes toward economic reforms, trust in institutions, governance, inequality, and living conditions after the collapse of communism and during an ongoing transition process.

The survey has been done in four waves so far:

- LiTS I (2006)
- LiTS II (2010)
- LiTS III (2016)
- LiTS IV (2022)

Together, these surveys cover more than 40 countries, mostly in Eastern Europe, Central Asia, and the Balkans, but also include some Western European countries for comparison. Each wave includes interviews with around 1,000 to 1,500 people per country.

The Life in Transition Survey collects Data on different metrics that play a role in the lives of the interviewed persons. A few examples are:

- Life satisfaction and household income
- Political opinions and trust in government
- Access to jobs, education, and digital tools
- Attitudes about democracy, markets, and climate change (in later waves)

All four waves used a random sampling method, with different regions and types of towns included. This means the results are supposed to represent the general adult population of each country. The surveys were done through face-to-face interviews using trained staff, and in the local language.

Each wave has files in the Stata and CSV format, and comes with a Codebook, a Questionnaire and a technical report. The dataset is mostly cross-sectional, which means that different people are interviewed each time and not the same people across years. The data is well organized and easy to use. There are some small differences between countries and years, for example some countries skipped a few questions or changed answer options slightly. The data is free and publicly available. The license allows a noncommercial academic use. The data is in a good format for reuse. It can be used for analysis on a national level and for comparisons between countries.

Countries covered by Discuss Data that are included in the LiTS:

Armenia (2006, 2010, 2016, 2022)

Azerbaijan (2006, 2010, 2016, 2022)

Belarus (2006, 2010, 2016, 2022)

Georgia (2006, 2010, 2016, 2022)

Kazakhstan (2006, 2010, 2016, 2022)

Kyrgyzstan (2006, 2010, 2016, 2022)

Moldova (2006, 2010, 2016, 2022)

Russia (2006, 2010, 2016, 2022)

Tajikistan (2006, 2010, 2016, 2022)

Ukraine (2006, 2010, 2016, 2022)

Uzbekistan (2006, 2010, 2016, 2022)

LiTS is used in a variety of different topics and research fields for example in studies about public trust and democracy, participation and satisfaction analysis of a government and for a comparison between post socialist countries. It has a strong versatile use because it's one of the few surveys that collects long term, comparable data from transition countries, with many useful topics. A few of those publications are bundled in the following bibliography:

- Adserà, A./ Boarini, R./ Dukart, J. (2017): The LiTS survey: A decade of measuring transition. CEPR VoxEU. <https://cepr.org/voxeu/columns/lits-survey-decade-measuring-transition>

- Cojocaru, A. (2014): Prospects of upward mobility and preferences for redistribution: Evidence from the Life in Transition Survey, In: European Journal of Political Economy, Vol. 34, 300-314.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0176268014000287>
- Gugushvili, D./ Lukac, M./ van Oorschot, W. (2021): Perceived welfare deservingness of needy people in transition countries: Comparative evidence from the Life in Transition Survey 2016. In: Global Social Policy, Vol. 21-2, 234–257. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468018121989520>
- Guriev, S./ Melnikov, N. (2018): Happiness convergence in transition countries, In: Journal of Comparative Economics, Vol: 46-3, 683-707.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0147596718302373>
- Nikolova, E./ Sanfey P. (2016): How much should we trust life satisfaction data? Evidence from the Life in Transition Survey. In: Journal of Comparative Economics, Vol. 44-3, 720-731.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0147596715001122>
- Recher, V. (2021): History Matters: Life Satisfaction in Transition Countries. In: Journal of Happiness Studies, Vol. 23, 171–193. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-021-00393-2>

EBRD (2006–2024): Life in Transition Survey (LiTS I–IV).

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